

Results of the Workshop on Alternative Business Models for Sustainable Tourism in Salar (Granada)

SWOT ANALYSIS (PRESENT DAY)

STRENGTHS

- **Strong community engagement** and high levels of social capital.
- **Significant** cultural and architectural **heritage**.
- **Prestige and recognition associated with the Roman villa** as a key element of local identity and attraction.
- **Rich living cultural traditions** (Carnival, Livestock Fair, Holy Week, etc.).
- A strong and well-defined **community identity**.
- **Privileged geographical location**.
- A **landscape of high cultural and environmental value**, with strong potential for the development of cultural routes.
- **A Long-term heritage project**.
- **Effective collaboration** with neighbouring municipalites.

WEAKNESSES

- **Mistrust** of the project among the local population due to limit access to clear and direct information.
- **Uncertainty** regarding the management, accessibility and public use of the heritage site.
- A **poorly defined tourism model** with limit differentiation.
- **An insufficient tourism offer**, particularly in traditional gastronomy and nature-based tourism.
- **Lack of basic infrastructure** to support visits the Roman villa.
- **Limited generational renewal** and insufficient support for youth entrepreneurship.

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- Development of **hostels and guesthouses**.
- **Growing interest in cultural tourism**.
- **Sustainable use** of natural resources and cultural heritage.
- Salar's **favourable geographical location**.
- **A rich combination of heritage, landscape, and gastronomy**.
- Promotion of **new business initiatives**.
- **Encouragement of active community involvement**.
- Organisation of **workshops and training activities** by the Town Council.
- **Revaluation and revitalisation** of the rural environment.
- **Depopulation** viewed as an **opportunity** for new development projects.
- The village positioned as an **attractive place** for young people to live.
- Renovation of vacant houses as **tourist accommodation** managed by local associations.

OPORTUNITIES

- **Lack** of hostels and accommodations
- **Competition** form rival destinations
- **Limited involvement** of local population
- Ongoing **depopulation** process
- **Risk of excessive and poorly managed tourism**.
- **Dependence on tour operators focused on mass tourism**.
- **Insufficient local services**.
- Shortage of rental housing.
- **Lack of training** in the tourism sector.
- **Insufficient training and awareness-raising** in schools and families.
- **Low levels of motivation** among young people.

THREATS

Results of the Workshop on Alternative Business Models for Sustainable Tourism in Salar (Granada)

SWOT ANALYSIS (IN TWO YEARS)

STRENGTHS

- **A Roman villa of outstanding significance** and in a good state of conservation.
- **High** heritage, cultural, and social **value**.
- **Strategic location** within Salar's heritage framework and an attractive cultural environment.
- **Strong potential for sustainable tourism** and an increase in visitor numbers.
- Development of **longer and more in-depth** guided tours.
- Capacity for social participation and interaction with local groups and stakeholders.
- Use of social media for **dissemination and promotion**.

WEAKNESSES

- **Lack of an effective communication and coordination network** between the Roman villa and the rest of the heritage assets.
- **Poor access to the Roman Villa of Salar**.
- **Insufficient infrastructure for visitor services** and site management.
- **Limited consolidation** of the site as a tourist destination.
- **Weak transport links and hospitality services** in the surrounding area.
- **Population decline and demographic scarcity**.
- **Lack of tourism diversification**.
- **Weak integration with other cultural activities** in the surrounding area.

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- Optimisation of **existing resources** through **local associations** and training actions oriented towards sustainable growth.
- **Development of complementary activities** linked to hospitality, guided services, and accommodation.
- **Increased awareness among the local population** of the value of Salar's cultural and heritage resources.
- **Attraction of external investment** to improve infrastructure, services, and facilities.
- Creation of **green pedestrian access routes** between Salar and the Roman villa, promoting sustainable mobility and enhancing the visitor experience.
- Strengthening opportunities related to accommodation, gastronomy, crafts, and local traditions.
- **Expansion and diversification** of the range of cultural activities linked to the Roman villa.
- **Greater flexibility in opening hours** for group visits as an opportunity to increase and diversify demand.

OPPORTUNITIES

- **Insufficient physical resources** at the interpretation centre, limiting its operation and capacity as a cultural space.
- **Lack of accessibility** both at the Roman villa and within the town of Salar.
- **Scarcity of activities aimed at specific target audiences** interested in the Villa and the town, reducing demand diversification.
- Dependence on a **single access route** or main road, with connectivity and wayfinding issues.
- Risk that existing strengths, if not improved and updated, may become threats in the medium term.
- **Limitations in available payment methods** at the Roman villa.

THREATS